

ADVANCEMENTS IN CIVIL EXPLOSIVES: NOVEL FORMULATIONS AND SUSTAINABLE FUEL SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT. The article presents the development of a new explosive mixture based on agricultural ammonium nitrate, possessing high detonation capability, increased water resistance, and physical stability. The concept for its creation is based on obtaining an oil-in-water (O/W) type microemulsion, produced using vegetable oil. Calculations conducted showed that the use of 100 % rapeseed oil methyl esters compared to diesel fuel improves emulsification by 14 %, reducing emulsification time by 15 %. Due to the structure of the microemulsion, ordinary agricultural ammonium nitrate can successfully retain around 7.5 % of the microemulsion. This amount of fuel phase is sufficient for obtaining an explosive composition with an appropriate oxygen balance. Substituting the porous ammonium nitrate (PAN) with agricultural ammonium nitrate - the cheapest oxidizer for the production of the newly developed explosive mixture, reduces its production cost and significantly increases the competitiveness of the product.

Key words: ANFO, ammonium nitrate, microemulsion, plant oil

Introduction

The most common explosives for industrial blasting are those that contain ammonium nitrate (AN) and diesel fuel (DF) in their composition - known as ANFO. The simple production technology and low price of raw materials used to produce them have made them indispensable for working in dry drilling and blasting holes in rocks with low and medium hardness.

As a rule, porous granulated ammonium nitrate (PAN) is used in the production of ANFO. The main technological feature of PAN is its ability to absorb diesel fuel (DF) in amounts known to be around 5.5 %, depending on the porosity of the granules. Bulk density, static strength of granules, fluidity, etc., play an important role in the quality of ANFO (Fabin and Jarocz, 2021).

Production of PAN is organised in many parts of the world, but its cost is typically 1.3-1.5 times higher than that of ammonium nitrate intended for agricultural purposes.

The disadvantage of ANFO mixtures produced with ordinary (agricultural) ammonium nitrate lies in their low detonation ability, and in many cases, low levels of physical stability of the charge associated with the attenuation of the combustible grain phase of ammonium nitrate and the removal of diesel fuel by airflow during air blast loading of holes (Buczkowski and Zygmunt, 2011).

When using low-quality PAN, whether technical or agricultural, after loading into the drill hole, the diesel fuel runs down to the bottom, disrupting the homogeneity of the explosive along the boreholes. Excess diesel fuel accumulates at the bottom of the drill hole, while deficits occur in its upper part. This increases the risk of insufficient ignition, and the detonation velocity and power emission are altered along the boreholes. The total emitted energy will be less than when working with high-quality PAN.

Lastly, we must note the increased release of toxic gases from the bottom of the boreholes, which form a cloud containing CO and soot, and at the top of the poles, NO_x emissions result in yellow smoke (Biessikirski et al., 2020; Ali et al., 2021).

Materials and methods

The type of fuel (mineral or vegetable oil, diesel fuel - DF) affects product quality, especially the explosive properties such as sensitivity to detonation, explosion velocity, and composition and quantity of leaking gas during the blast. The fuel must have flash points above 60 °C. Fuel viscosity also affects ANFO explosives. An increase in fuel viscosity reduces the absorbing capacity of the AN, while low viscosity enhances absorption. Mixing of AN and fuel is carried out mechanically, aiming for an even distribution of fuel. Poor mixing can result in unexpected initiation, reduced blast power, and increased quantities of poisonous gas leaking during the explosion (Zygmunt and Buczkowski, 2012).

Another issue with ANFO mixtures is the strong electrification of the nitrate and fuel particles in the airflow during pneumatic loading of blast holes and drillings. Electrification is caused by the dielectric properties of nitrate and fuel. The concentration of static electricity charges on the surface of the explosive material could lead to emergency situations. Separation and removal of the combustible phase by the airflow during pneumatic loading is due to the low adhesion of diesel fuel to the surface of the granules of AN (Li et al. 2023).

To address the deficiencies listed so far, a new explosive based on ordinary ammonium nitrate and a fuel microemulsion prepared by special technology has been developed.

Harnessing rapeseed oil for sustainable explosive production

An analysis has been conducted on the potential use of various alternative fuels for explosive production, with particular attention given to fuels derived from renewable sources. These liquid fuels are derived from the biomass of plant seeds. In most cases, these fuels exhibit significant differences from traditional liquid hydrocarbon fuels in their physicochemical properties, which impact both the organisation of production processes and the determination of the technical, economic, and environmental parameters of explosive production (Marchenko et al., 2001; Li et al. 2023).

Rapeseed oil (RSO) emerges as one of the most promising alternatives as an energy source, presenting a robust competition to diesel fuel commonly used in the production of similar explosives. It serves as a key component of the oil phase in the emulsion of the novel explosive mixture. Rapeseed oil boasts a higher calorific value compared to diesel, it is non-toxic, and biodegradable (degraded by microorganisms). Notably, it lacks sulphur compounds entirely, unlike ordinary diesel fuel, which contains 3 % sulphur. Carbon monoxide emissions, a hazardous gas, are on average 48 % lower when rapeseed oil is burned compared to regular diesel fuel (Marchenko et al., 2001).

Rapeseed oil's high heat capacity enhances its active interaction with ammonium nitrate during the explosive reaction, while its moderate viscosity enables easy absorption by ammonium nitrate (Marchenko et al., 2001).

In the development of the new explosive mixture, rapeseed oil was chosen for its economic advantage and reduced environmental impact. By promoting environmental conservation, the use of rapeseed oil — a cheaper, environmentally friendly alternative not subjected to taxation like petroleum fuels — provides a strong economic incentive for its adoption.

The analysis conducted by me determined that a prospective alternative fuel for explosive production is the fuel obtained by mixing liquid hydrocarbon fuels with derivatives of rapeseed oil - methyl esters of rapeseed oil (MER). Parameters influencing evaporation, emulsification, and "combustion" processes include fuel density (ρ), kinematic viscosity (ν), dynamic viscosity (μ), and surface tension (σ).

To obtain MER, RSO underwent two purification stages: refining and bleaching. Subsequently, through transesterification of rapeseed oil glycerides with methanol at a temperature of 80-90 °C in the presence of KOH, a mixture of methyl esters of liquid acids from RSO was obtained. Determination of all parameters of RSO, MER, and DF, as well as their mixtures, was conducted using traditional laboratory apparatus and conditions. Density was measured in density meters with an accuracy of 0.001 g/cm³, kinematic viscosity was determined using a glass capillary viscosity meter, and surface tension - using a Rebinder instrument. The chromatographic analysis of a rapeseed oil (RSO) sample was conducted using the multidimensional KONIK K2 HPLC+GC system. This allowed for the determination of the qualitative and quantitative composition of fatty acids affecting the composition of rapeseed oil: hexadecanoic (palmitic) - 4.83%; octadecanoic (stearic) - 1.72%; 9-octadecenoic (oleic) - 43.72%; 9,12-octadecadienoic (linoleic) - 20.92%; 9,12,15-octadecatrienoic (linolenic) - 8.52%; gadoleic (eicosenoic) - 4.81%; erucic (erucic) - 14.01%; unidentified residue - 1.47%.

Tables 1 and 2 provide the physicochemical parameters of RSO, MER, DF, and their mixtures in the temperature range 20 - 70 °C. Data within the temperature range 50 - 70°C are essential for calculating evaporation and emulsification processes since the fuel is heated up to these temperatures during emulsification (Mitkov, 2020).

The second stage of the conducted research pertains to the analysis of the influence of differences in the values of ρ , ν , μ , and σ on the alternative biodiesel. The data presented in Table 2 allow for a qualitative assessment of the impact of these indicators.

They demonstrate that the dynamic viscosity of MER is twice as large as that of DF.

Table 1. *Physical and chemical characteristics of DF and MER*

Indicators	DF	MER
Density kg/m ³ at t=20 °C	826	877
Kinematic viscosity, at m ² /s at t = 20°C	3.83	8.0
Surface tension, N/m, 20 °C	27.1 x 10 ⁻³	30.7 x 10 ⁻³
Cetane number, not less than	45	48
Flash point, not less than, °C	60	56
Solidification point, not more than, °C	-10	-8
Coking - 10 % residue, not more than	0.5	0.3
Acidity, mg KOH/g	0.06	0.5
Content, %		
Sulphur, not more than	0.2	0.02
Ash, not more than	0.02	0.02
Water	----	----
Total glycerin content, % (max)	----	0,3
Heat of combustion, MJ/kg	42.5	37.1

Table 2. *Physical and chemical characteristics of mixtures of MER and DF*

Fuel Composition	Density, ρ , kg/m ³			Kinematic viscosity, ν , m ² /s		
	20°	50°	70°	20°	50°	70°
RSO	913	891	878	--	--	17.4
MER	877	856	842	8.0	4.25	3.1
DF	826	805	791	3.83	2.11	1.67
30%MER+70%DF	841	821	806	4.87	2.67	2.1
50%MER+50%DF	851	830	816	5.62	2.97	2.38
75%MER+25%DF	864	843	829	6.93	3.68	2.74
Fuel Composition	Dynamic viscosity, μ , Pa.s x 10 ⁱ			Surface tension, γ , N/m x 10 ⁱ		
Temperature	20°	50°	70°	20°	50°	
RSO	--	--	15.3	33.2	31.8	
MER	7.02	3.64	2.61	30.7	29.2	
DF	3.16	1.7	1.32	27.1	25.3	
30%MER+70%DF	4.1	2.19	1.69	27.8	26.0	
50%MER+50%DF	4.78	2.46	1.94	28.6	26.9	
75%MER+25%DF	5.99	3.1	2.27	29.5	27.8	

The increase in viscosity leads to an acceleration of the combustion rate during the explosive reaction (Mitkov, 2020). The 14% increase in surface tension of MER compared to DF is a cause of the increased heterogeneity of fuel dispersion (emulsification). The density of MER is 6 % higher than that of DF, guaranteeing a higher density of the explosive.

Using the Python software tool for deriving mathematical dependencies and data processing, a quantitative assessment

of the impact of ρ , σ , and μ on fuel characteristics was conducted. The calculations indicate that utilising 100 % MER, as opposed to DF, results in a 14 % improvement in emulsification, thus reducing emulsification time by 15 %.

For a preliminary assessment of the lowest heat of combustion of MER, the structural formulae of methyl esters and hydrocarbons of similar molecular weight of petroleum origin were analysed. As an example, we will consider the structural formulae of erucic acid, its methyl ester, and the hydrocarbon belonging to the class of alkenes.

Erucic acid $C_{22}H_{42}O_2$:

Ester $C_{23}H_{44}O_2$:

Hydrocarbon $C_{23}H_{44}$:

As can be seen, the structural formulae of the hydrocarbon and the ester differ in that the group CH_3 is replaced by the group $COOCH_3$, which predisposes the ester to differences in physicochemical properties and especially in calorific value. This is because MER is an oxygen-containing compound, and the lowest heat of combustion of esters is slightly lower than that of DF. If DF contains about 0.4 % oxygen, then in the methyl ester of oleic acid, for example, it is 10.8 %, and in the methyl ester of erucic acid, it is 9.1 % (Marchenko et al., 2001). Therefore, esters with the highest possible calorific value can be obtained from technical RSO. The use of mixtures of RSO and DF is limited due to increased viscosity and coking of rapeseed oil.

Creating a new micro-emulsion

The key components of the micro-emulsion type "oil in water" are as follows: a mixture of petroleum and vegetable oil (75 to 80 %); ammonium nitrate (4 to 9 %); urea (8 to 12 %); surfactants (0.1 to 0.5 %); water (5.9 to 8.5 %).

The structure of the combustion phase is a micro-emulsion of the "oil in water" type. The micro-particles of this emulsion have an outer shell comprising an aqueous mineral-organic solution and a dispersed internal phase, which includes liquid fuel. Essentially, we have tiny droplets of fuel dispersed in an aqueous solution.

Due to the high penetrating power of this type of emulsion, there is no need for porous ammonium nitrate to be used. The dispersion phase of the emulsion, consisting of liquid fuel, permeates throughout its whole volume, facilitated by capillary action through micro-pores and micro-granules or crystals of ammonium nitrate (Resende et al. 2014; Mitkov, 2020).

Figure 1 visualizes the studies that have been carried out. To track the even distribution of fuel in the pores of the AN, 5-10 ppm of a colouring agent is added. Two graduated cylinders are filled with agricultural AN, but in the first one, a micro-emulsion of the O/W type is added in the amount of 5.5 % (the content of the fuel phase in classic ANFO) in relation to ammonium nitrate, while in the second one, the same amount of diesel fuel is added.

Figure 1a shows that using an O/W type microemulsion achieves homogeneity throughout the entire cylinder column,

which ensures good initiation, consistent detonation velocity, and energy release while minimizing toxic gases.

Fig. 1. Comparative study of the absorbent capacity of AAN; a) - mixed with 5.5 % emulsion, b) - 5.5 % mixed with diesel

In contrast, adding diesel fuel, as shown in Figure 1b, results in non-uniformity — the diesel fuel settles at the bottom, leaving an insufficient amount at the top. This decreases the detonation velocity and energy release, and significantly increases the amount of toxic gases produced during the explosion.

The characteristics of the new explosive were tested through standardized density measurements, open charge diameter assessments in polyethylene sheaths, and detonation velocity experiments using the MicroTrap measurement system.

Results and discussion

Experimentally, it has been proven that the required amount of micro-emulsion to ensure the necessary functionality of ANFO explosive is 7.5 %. Such a quantity of the fuel phase is sufficient to achieve explosive draw with a zero oxygen balance.

During the studies, it was found that the fuel emulsion possesses the properties of an electrolyte, and explosive devices based on it are unlikely to accumulate static electricity charges on their surface during the production process, transportation, and immediate loading.

Test results of the research on the newly developed explosive and all known explosives of this kind for civilian use are provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparative characteristics of new explosive and other coarse-dispersed explosives

Product Name	Bulk density, g/cm ³	Critical diameter, mm	Velocity of detonation, km/s	Specific electrical resistance, $\Omega \cdot m$	Harmful gases, 1/kg
New explosive	0.95-0.98	60-70	3.4-3.6	150-200	60
GDA 79/21	0.85-0.90	50-70	3.2-3.6	105	70
ANFO L	0.92-0.96	60-80	2.8-3.2	104	80

The data in Table 3 demonstrate that the new explosive has a higher density, a smaller diameter for an open charge in a polyethylene sheath, and a higher detonation velocity. The high detonation capability of the explosive mixture is attributed to the penetration of the emulsion type "oil in water" into the internal structure of the AN. The solids of the AN, upon interaction with the fuel water-oil phase, gain the ability to absorb and retain components of the water-oil emulsion. This even distribution of liquid fuel in the structure of the oxidation stage ensures optimal conditions for the completeness of the reaction in the explosive transformation.

Studies on the physicochemical properties and characteristics of combinations of such explosives have shown that the main indicators developed exceed those of known analogues.

The high safety and low toxicity of the developed explosive mixture are attributed to the use of water-oil emulsion type O/W, where the liquid fuel phase is dispersed in a large volume of water-mineral solution, acting as an electrolyte with high power conductivity.

During the storage period of six months, no changes in the new explosive physical properties and explosive characteristics have been observed. Furthermore, there are no alterations in its appearance, no signs of material sintering, and no separation of the liquid phase, while the strength of the granules remains intact.

Conclusions

Through the utilisation of hygroscopic properties of ammonium nitrate, a novel technology has emerged, enabling the absorption and retention of sustainable fuels in the form of an emulsion. This emulsion, functioning as an electrolyte, prevents electrification of the explosives, facilitating their pneumatic (mechanical) loading.

A pioneering technology has been devised to produce a micro-emulsion of the "oil in water" (O/W) type. This innovation enables deep penetration and retention within the grains of ammonium nitrate.

The newly developed explosive exhibits a small critical diameter of 50-57 mm, rendering it suitable not only for open mines and quarries but also for loading blast holes in underground conditions and specialised blasting operations.

Further research endeavours are warranted to deepen our understanding of all aspects of the new explosive, including opportunities for synergistic use with other components to enhance its explosive characteristics.

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